

Polarographic Determination of Metronidazole and Chloramphenicol

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A detailed study of the polarographic behaviour of chloramphenicol has been reported¹. Previous studies² report application of polarography to the analysis of chloramphenicol in pharmaceutical preparations. It is reported³ that the reduction peak of chloramphenicol is pH dependent in its determination by DPP.

A suitable polarographic analysis of metronidazole has been carried out by DPP technique. Metronidazole has also been determined by dc polarography at pH 2. A DPP method⁶ for the determination of metronidazole in biological fluid has also been reported. Faith *et al.*⁷ studied metronidazole by polarography in tablets. Papas and Delaney⁸ proposed a DPP method for metronidazole by using 0.2 M potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer. Bishop and Hussein⁹ studied metronidazole at rotating disc electrodes. They studied voltammetrically the reduction of metronidazole at a gold electrode in alkaline medium. Abu-Zuhri *et al.*¹⁰ proposed a dc polarographic method for estimation of metronidazole in pharmaceuticals.

The present study reports simple and rapid dc polarographic methods for determination of chloramphenicol and metronidazole, which are applicable for their determination in marketed formulations.

TABLE I—VALUES OF STATISTICAL PARAMETERS*

Drug	Concn. of drug sample $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	R.M.D.	S.D.	C.V.
Chloramphenicol	40	2.51	0.053	2.73
	120	2.10	0.042	2.10
Metronidazole	40	1.75	0.078	2.10
	120	1.08	0.048	1.29

* Calculated from ten identical experiments.

The method for the polarographic determination of chloramphenicol and metronidazole is simple, rapid and convenient as compared to other reported polarographic methods. The studies in acetate buffer showed well-defined sigmoid shaped polarograms. The linearity of current concentration relationship was observed over a fairly wide concentration range. The merit of the method is implied from the accuracy with which the drug was determined from marketed formulations both by calibration curve method and standard addition method. The method is highly precise and accurate as is evident from the R.M.D. and S.D. values (Table 1).

Experimental

Voltammetric analysis was carried out with an Elico CL-25D instrument using DME and SCE electrode system.

All measurements were carried out at $28 \pm 1^\circ$. Triton X-100 (0.1%) was used as a maximum suppressor. The drug samples used were pure and supplied by Chemopharma Laboratories and Pharmachem Laboratories, Bombay.

For both chloramphenicol and metronidazole, a 0.1% drug solution (2 ml) was mixed with 0.1% solution of Triton-X-100 (1 ml) and acetate buffer (25 ml) of pH 4.5. The volume was made upto 50 ml with double-distilled water. The solution was deoxygenated by passing N_2 gas for 20 min. The solution containing $40 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the drug was then transferred to a polarographic cell and the polarogram was recorded. Chloramphenicol and metronidazole showed a well-defined polarogram with $E_{1/2}$ -0.42 and -0.48 V vs SCE with diffusion current of 1.9 and 3.7 μA respectively.

Studies were carried out in different supporting electrolyte solutions such as acetate buffer, borate buffer, Britton-Robinson buffer and McIlvaine buffer at various pH values. In the acetate buffer of pH 4.5, the drugs gave well-defined sigmoid shaped polarograms with maximum value of diffusion current. Hence this buffer was chosen as a supporting electrolyte.

For calibration curve method, different volumes of 0.1% drug solution were taken and polarograms were recorded corresponding to the concentrations 40, 80, 120, 160 and 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The current-concentration curve was found to be linear in the concentration range of 40 to 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

The present method was further extended for the quantification of the drugs in marketed pharmaceutical formulations. The amount of the drug in the marketed samples was determined by calibration curve method and also by standard addition method.

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